

A Study on Awareness Among Small Retailers About Implementation of HUID (Hallmarking Unique ID)

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ABSTRACT

BIS is the National Standard Body of India established under the BIS Act 2016 for the harmonious development of the activities of standardization, marking and quality certification of goods and for matters connected therewith or incidental thereto BIS has been providing traceable and tangible benefits to the national economy in a number of ways – providing safe reliable quality goods; minimizing health hazards to consumers; promoting exports and imports substitute; control over proliferation of varieties etc. through standardization, certification and testing.

The **BIS hallmark** is a hallmarking system for gold as well as silver jewellery sold in India certifying the purity of the metal. It certifies that the piece of jewellery conforms to a set of standards laid by the Bureau of Indian Standards, the national standards organization of India. India is the second biggest market for gold and its jewellery. India imports in excess of 1000 tons annually (including unofficially smuggled gold) with negligible local production. The annual gold imports are around 50 billion US\$ next only to crude oil imports widening the trade deficit.

The BIS system of hallmarking of gold jewellery began in April 2000. The standard specifications governing this system are IS 1417 (Grades of Gold and Gold Alloys, Jewellery/Artefacts), IS 1418 (Assaying of Gold in Gold Bullion, Gold alloys and Gold Jewellery/Artefacts), IS 2790 (Guidelines for Manufacture of 14, 18 and 22 carat Gold Alloys only), IS 3095 (Gold solders for use in manufacture of jewellery).

Keywords: BIS hallmark, jewellery and Standard

Objectives of the study:

- ✓ To determine the knowledge among small retailers about the new HALLMARKING SCHEME (HUID).
- ✓ To compare the old and new Hallmarking Scheme.
- ✓ To analyze the new process of Hallmarking.

Scope of the Study:

The basic scope of this study is to know the impact among small retailers and customers after implementing HUID (**Hallmarking Unique Identification**). The study also says about the process of applying License to HUID and Hallmarking Jewelry under registered HCs (**Hallmarking Centers**).

Statement of The Problem:

The current experience of those who have tried to embrace the HUID system is painful.....there is a huge time lag between giving the product and the receipt of the physical product....3 to 4 days is a very long delay as compared to a maximum of 7 to 8 hours within which the product is tested and hallmarked in the current scenario.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The data is collected only from respondents living in Coimbatore city. So it cannot represent the whole population.
- ✓ The time limit is short period.

Research Methodology:

The research design is descriptive which includes surveys and fact findings enquires of different kind. Descriptive research studies are those which are concerned with describing the characteristics of a particular individual or a group.

SAMPLE DESIGN:

A sample design is a technique of the procedure for the research would adopt in selecting item for the sample.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Convenience Sampling:

Convenience Sampling is the matter of taking what you can get. It is an accidental sample although selection may be unguided, in probably is not random; using the correct definition of everyone in the population having is equal chance of being selected. Volunteers would constitute a convenience sample. The data collected was both Primary and Secondary

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Akshaya Tritiya (2022): What you need to know about buying gold today: As per Hindu mythology, it is considered auspicious to buy gold on Akshaya Tritiya. In 2022, this auspicious day falls on May 3 i.e., today. An individual can buy gold either in the physical form (jewellery, coins, bars) or in the paper form (Gold ETFs, Gold mutual funds, SGBs, Digital gold). If you are planning to buy gold today, here's all you need to keep in mind.

V. Vijay Durga Prasad, (2010), in his study on "Hallmarking in India: A Major Quality Initiative in the Largest Gold Jewellery Market in India is predominantly a market for buying and selling physical gold and gold in the form of Ornaments in the market for ornaments and jewellery, consumer protection is not assured, cheating on caratage is a widespread problem, although it has received much policy attention in last few years but the problem continues. purchased from traditional jewelers and the situation became grave after the abolishment of Gold Control Act in the early 1990s, when a lot of jewelers mushroomed in various parts of the gold jewelers tried to compromise on purity of the jewellery

What is Hallmarking?

Hallmark is an official mark used as a guarantee of purity or fineness of precious metal articles. According to BIS, —Hallmarking is the accurate determination and official recording of the proportionate content of precious metal in precious metal articles. It is now mandatory for gold jewellery and artefacts of 14K, 18K and 22K to be hallmarked. Steps have been initiated for amendment to Indian Standards that would permit hallmarking of other caratages too.

The hallmarking stamp, which so far has four symbols — BIS logo; purity in carat (K) and fineness; the identification mark of the AHC and jeweller's stamp — will have the last two stamps replaced by a six-digit alphanumeric HUID, with which every article would have to be separately tagged. Jewellery below 2 gm has been exempted, as also jadau, kundan and polki jewellery techniques and designs. The jewellers found flouting the guidelines will be fined a minimum of Rs2 lakh and can be punished with up to a two-year jail term while the recognition of the AHC that had faulted may be cancelled depending on the quantum of failure. In due course, one can check the quality of gold jewellery on the BIS Care app by keying in the HUID. It is like an Aadhaar card or a property document, says Ramesh Kalyanaraman, chairman and MD of Kalyan Jewellers, adding that organised players are likely to benefit more since they have already been hallmarking the jewellery. —There may be teething issues like changing the inventory and reworking the logistics, but for a brand like ours, things will not change much, he adds.

Growth of Hallmarking Scheme

As on 31 December 2021, around 1 lakh 30 thousand Jewellers have taken registration from BIS for selling hallmarked jewellery and artefacts while 1004 BIS recognized assaying and hallmarking centers are operative in the country. In the past, in a year maximum number of jewellery hallmarked was 4.49

crore in the year 2018-2019. However, after the launch of automation software, around 5.5 crore jewellery have been hallmarked with HUID in the period from 1st July 2021 to 31 December 2021

HUID

HUID(Hallmarking Unique ID) is a unique code that will be given to every piece of jewellery at the time of hallmarking, which will be helpful in identifying the jeweller and the Assaying and Hallmarking Centres (AHCs) which had hallmarked the jewellery. It will be a six-digit alphanumeric code, with which every piece of jewellery will be tagged. According to jewellers, while the government had assured that the process of HUID will be restricted to AHCs, they too are involved in it, as they have to tag their inventory (each of them) with a unique ID and upload the details on the BIS website and then send it to AHCs for hallmarking.

Jewellers say the HUID process has increased the time required to get the hallmarking on jewels and this has created huge backlogs at AHCs. Earlier, we would send products on Monday and get the hallmarked product the next day, but now we have to wait till Wednesday, said Ishu Datwani, Founder of Anmol Jewels.

HUID number : According to the Department of Consumer Affairs website, the Hallmark Unique Identification (HUID) number is a six-digit Alphanumeric code made up of letters and digits. Every item of jewellery will be issued a HUID number at the moment of hallmarking, and each one will be unique. At the Assaying & Hallmarking centre, the jewellery is hand stamped with the unique number. A unique identifier (HUID) is assigned to each piece of jewellery, allowing for traceability. It's crucial for Hallmarking's legitimacy and dealing with complaints about the purity of Hallmarked jewellery.

In HUID-based Hallmarking, jewellers are automatically registered without the need for human intervention. Its purpose is to ensure the purity of Hallmarked jewellery and to detect any fraud. HUID is a safe system that doesn't jeopardise data privacy or security, according to the Department of Consumer Affairs.

New hallmarking rules

The government has made it mandatory for jewellers to hallmark gold jewellery, but with some relaxations. Jewellers with an annual turnover of up to Rs 40 lakh will be exempted from mandatory hallmarking. Similarly, jewellery for international exhibitions and government-approved business-to-business domestic exhibitions will also be exempted.

Watches, fountain pens and special types of jewellery, such as Kundan, Polki and Jadau, have also been granted relaxation under the new regulations. It will also allow hallmarking of additional carats -- 20, 23, and 24.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN Rate a score for HUID, Rate a score for old

Hallmarking Scheme and Rate your knowledge in HUID:

	Rate a score for HUID	Rate a score for old Hallmarking Scheme	Rate your knowledge in HUID
Rate a score for HUID	1	-0.1650339081	-0.06299282114
Rate a score for old Hallmarking Scheme	-0.1650339081	1	0.04943811848
Rate your knowledge in HUID	-0.06299282114	0.04943811848	1

From the above table we observed there is a (-0.16503) significant and moderately strong negative correlation between Rate a score for old hallmarking scheme and Rate your knowledge in HUID.

SUGGESTIONS

- All Entry & Exit of materials at the AHM centers should be entered in the Portal without fail.
- All Payments to be routed through the BIS Portal and AHM Centers receive their charges after deduction of BIS fee.
- Once BIS reaches the 100% mandatory Hallmarking target, HUID can be implemented phase by phase reducing the exemptions so that every entity will be a part of the system in a couple of years and there will be no Administrative or Revenue Issue.

CONCLUSION

HUID is only applicable in India. Due to this implementation of HUID retailers can sell only government authorised/approved gold jewells. The new terms and conditions of BIS are more complicated to the retailers. Only those who have a man power or doing business in Corporate level can follow all the conditions. Hence I conclude that HUID is good for Jewellery but it'll take more time and knowledge to implement it and followed by all. So the BIS organization should give required time.

References

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